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Wastewater Treatment Plant and Its Implementation Strategy-A Case Study of Centurion University of Technology and Management

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Introduction: The rising water scarcity not only creates problems for the human being but also creates major challenges for the growth of the entire eco-system (1-5). So there is an urgent need of finding out an alternative use of used water for domestics as well as agricultural practices. The present study carried out a dynamic approach constructing a wastewater treatment plant in Centurion University of Technology and Management (CUTM), Paralakhemundi campus, Odisha and its utilization for agricultural activities.

Methods: The treatment plant consist of bar and screen chamber, oil and grease tank, collection tank, sedimentation tank, filtration tank, and control panel The oil and grease is removed by using grease traps provided in the tank and the water free from coarse solids and oil are collected in collection tank of size 12×4.5×4 m. The collected water is let on to pass to the sedimentation tank of size 12×4.5×4 m for a detention period of 4hrs. By using the slow sand filter, the water is filtered in the filtration tank having dimensions 11.12×5.5×4 m. Now the water is ready for the usage by using electric motor in the control panel chamber of 11.12×3.5×4 m.

Results & Discussions: The present study has been done by constructing a wastewater treatment plant covering an area of 750 m². The campus comprises of 5 numbers of hostels, 3 hostel mess and 3 numbers of staff quarters where total population is more than 1500.. The supply of water per day is 279 cum and average waste generated is 9.29 cum/hr. By considering the peak factor as 3, the maximum design flow capacity is 27.89 cum/hr. The estimated cost comes to the tune of Rs. 25, 75,539.

Conclusions: The present study proves that by the construction of the wastewater treatment model the ground water can be saved for the future use and drinking. This wastewater treatment model requires less maintenance cost, operational cost and also eco-friendly. After treatment of water, treated water maintains the standards for agricultural practices and gardening purposes. It covers an area of 10 hectares under field crops, horticultural crops, planation crops, herbal garden, lawn and playground being irrigated from treatment plant.

Keywords: Wastewater treatment, bar and screen chamber, oil and grease tank, collection tank, sedimentation tank, filtration tank, and control panel

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